

A Review on Recycle of Waste To Make Prosthetics

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Abstract

The production of prosthetics using 3D printing technology has revolutionized the way prosthetics are manufactured. The use of recyclable plastics in this process has made it possible to create affordable, high-quality prosthetics for people in need around the world. This is particularly impactful in developing countries where traditional prosthetics can be expensive and difficult to obtain. In India, where the population has a high incidence of disabilities and traditional prosthetics can be prohibitively expensive, the use of 3D printing technology has gained popularity. The use of recycled plastics in the process has added to the sustainability of the process, reducing waste and making the process more environmentally friendly. Overall, the use of 3D printing and recyclable plastics in prosthetics production has opened up new possibilities for affordable, high-quality prosthetics, improving the lives of people with disabilities by providing them with life-changing prosthetics that may have been out of reach otherwise.

Keywords : prosthetics, 3D printing technology, recyclable plastics, sustainability

Introduction

Three-dimensional printing, or 3D printing, has revolutionized the manufacturing process, making it possible to create complex structures and designs quickly and efficiently (Fan et al., 2015). One area where 3D printing has had a significant impact is in the production of prosthetics. With the use of recyclable plastics, it has become possible to create affordable, high-quality prosthetics for people in need around the world. Around the world, there are many organizations and individuals using 3D printing technology to produce prosthetics for those who cannot afford them (Zagel et al., 2017). This has been particularly impactful in developing countries, where access to traditional prosthetics can be limited due to high costs and logistical challenges. With 3D printing, prosthetics can be produced on-site and tailored to the specific needs of each individual.

In India, there has been a growing interest in 3D printing technology for prosthetics production. The country has a large population with a high incidence of disabilities, and traditional prosthetics can be prohibitively expensive. 3D printing offers a more affordable and customizable solution, allowing for prosthetics to be produced quickly and efficiently (Sakib-Uz-Zaman and Khondoker, 2023). The use

of recyclable plastics in 3D printing for prosthetics production has added to the sustainability of the process. Many organizations are using recycled plastics to produce prosthetics, reducing waste and making the process more environmentally friendly.

Overall, the use of 3D printing and recyclable plastics in prosthetics production has opened up new possibilities for affordable, high-quality prosthetics around the world, including in India (Joseph et al., 2021). This technology has the potential to greatly improve the lives of people with disabilities, providing them with access to life-changing prosthetics that may have otherwise been out of reach.

Keywords: 3D printing, recyclable plastics, customizable solution, life-changing prosthetic.

PROSTHETICS MARKET IN THE WORLD

Analysis of different kinds of prosthetic market:

Active Upper Limb Prosthesis

The health care systems of developed nations provide access to all forms of active upper-limb prosthesis (e.g., Western and Northern Europe). Myoelectric/externally powered upper-limb prosthesis are regarded as standard of treatment in several nations. Yet, different coverage policies lead to different adoption levels. 80% to 90% of patients in nations with healthcare systems that pay for multiple upper-limb prostheses at once utilise myoelectrics as their main prosthesis. The percentage of myoelectric prostheses may drop to 50% to 60% if the healthcare system only pays for one prosthesis at a time (Kannenbergh, 2017). In industrialised nations with health care systems, body-powered devices are the only active upper-limb prostheses that can be used (e.g., United States, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Japan). Less than 35% to 40% of patients with active prosthesis in these nations commonly use myoelectric/externally powered prostheses, which require approved exceptions from coverage plans. Yet, the prevalence of myoelectric prosthesis may increase to as much as 70% in some specialist urban rehabilitation centres (Østlie et al., 2011).

Countries with healthcare systems that give the bulk of their beneficiaries inactive or no upper-limb prosthesis (e.g., Eastern Europe, Latin America, Asia, Africa). The adoption rates of active upper-limb prosthetic technologies vary dramatically between nations despite the fact that the scientific evidence supporting upper-limb prosthetics is the same everywhere. This is due to the vast differences in coverage policies and funding. The most significant variation across industrialised nations appears to be whether policies just take into account prosthetic function or additionally take into account psychosocial components when deciding the medical necessity of the available active prosthetic technologies and designs.

In conclusion, it is quite intriguing that while the scientific evidence on upper-limb prosthetics is the same around the world, prosthetic fitting and rehabilitation practises, funding, and coverage policies show a wide range from practically no access to prostheses to passive, body-powered, or myoelectric prostheses as the specific standard of care in the various regions and countries. The finance capabilities of the payer appear to be the primary determinant for the grade of upper-limb prosthetic care in the healthcare system of a given country(s). The degree of acknowledgment of the significance of the psychosocial elements of upper-limb amputations and its implications for the medical requirement of the various types of prosthetic technology and design appears to be the secondary factor (Desmond, 2007). The acceptance and rejection rates of upper-limb prostheses between different nations or regions, or between payers with different methods, are not known because there are no data on the effects of these various national or even payer-specific coverage and fitting practise techniques. Nonetheless, there is research to support the idea that fitting a functioning prosthesis as soon as possible following an upper-limb amputation may greatly enhance acceptance rates and the success of rehabilitation in general.

Lower limb prosthesis

Lower limb amputation is a common occurrence around the world and continues to pose a serious risk to morbidity and mortality. Thus, it has come to be acknowledged that a successful rehabilitation outcome requires the provision of high quality and efficient prosthetics services. The occurrence of amputations has been rising in Malaysia, and numerous key elements of service delivery (such service intervention and prosthetic staff) should be anticipated to meet the rising demand (Department of Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur et al., 2017). WHO estimates that 0.5% of people in developing nations have a disability that calls for the use of a prosthesis or orthosis as well as accompanying rehabilitation treatments. According to this forecast, almost 160,000 of Malaysia's 32 million people today may require prosthetic or orthotic devices. By 2040, the population is expected to total 38.5 million, with about 200,000 of them people having a physical impairment.

The growing desire for improved quality of life for people who are missing limbs has a favourable market impact on the management of the worldwide prosthetic company (Quintero-Quiroz and Pérez, 2019). According to the particular type of amputation, this has led to a significant technological progress in prosthetic componentry (such as prosthetic feet, knee joints, adapters, and liners). The price of a prosthesis in Malaysia normally ranges from RM400 to RM15,000, although it may be more expensive if sophisticated parts or computerised systems are utilised. Regrettably, West Malaysia is home to the majority of certified prosthetists and orthotists (CPOs), who can only offer the best services there. Some of them attempt to go to other regions of Malaysia, however even when the prostheses are of high quality, the cost of travel and other fees drives up the price. A sizable portion of amputees in Malaysia are financially burdened because to the high cost of prosthesis. Many of them are consequently forced to choose less functional, less expensive prosthesis, which impede their recovery.

Around 160,000 people in Malaysia are thought to require orthotic or prosthetic devices. Nevertheless, there are little public statistics on the number of people in this nation who now have a lower leg amputated and require a prosthetic device or prosthetic services. The National Orthopaedic Registry Malaysia Diabetic Foot 2009, which recorded 19 cases of upper and 405 cases of lower limb amputations owing to infections, is the sole source of amputation data that is currently accessible. These statistics only provide amputation records based on infections caused by diabetes for a single year (Quintero-Quiroz and Pérez, 2019). In Malaysia, no information is gathered on the number of amputees, the cause and extent of amputation, or the age, gender, and level of activity of those who have lost limbs. Rehabilitation teams could provide practical services to meet the requirements of people who have had their lower limbs amputated by using amputation records that reveal statistics and trends. In order to assess the effectiveness of the government's efforts to lower the incidence of lower limb amputation and suggest the steps required to improve the quality of prosthetic devices and services, statistical records at the national level would be very helpful for policymakers, the prosthetic industry, prosthetic service providers, and researchers.

MULTI-AXIS PROSTHETIC FOOT

There are more than 500,000 amputees in Sudan alone. Their chances of leading regular lives are reduced by barriers to employment and independent living as well as the absence of prosthetic organs in Africa. The price difference between expensive high-performance prosthetic feet in the European Union and the United States and cheap prosthetic feet of subpar quality, durability, and performance in underdeveloped countries is significant.

PROSTHETICS MARKET IN INDIA

The WHOQOL-Bref (World Health Organization Quality of Life-Bref) questionnaire is an adult-specific, condensed version of the WHOQOL-100. The instrument has 24 specific questions covering four self-assessed QOL domains: physical health (seven items), psychological (six items), social relationships (three items), and environment. It also has two general questions (one covering overall QOL and the other the person's general health situation) (eight items).

This study found that compared to people without disabilities, prosthetic and orthotic users had lower quality of life (QOL) scores in the areas of physical, psychological, and environmental health. In terms of overall QOL or general health, there were no appreciable differences between the groups with and without disabilities. In order to achieve equity, health, rehabilitation, and development programmes must give priority to the subgroups of disabled people with the lowest QOL ratings. These findings are consistent with a systematic review of the literature and a case-control study of leprosy patients in India using WHOQOL-Bref, both of which discovered that individuals with disabilities had lower QOL ratings in the physical health and psychological areas than the control group (Kumar and Vinita, 2021).

Poliomyelitis was the most frequent cause of impairment among the participants, leaving survivors with diminished muscular strength and varied degrees of paralysis who need a knee-ankle-foot orthosis. India was declared polio-free in 2014, however many individuals still struggle with polio-related impairments. As far as we are aware, only one previous study comparing the quality of life (QOL) of a group of lower-limb amputees with that of the Indian populace as a whole has been published. As a result, the discussion that follows focuses on prior research done in other pertinent nations.

The 36-Item Short Form Health Survey (SF-36) was used in a QOL research of lower limb amputees in Bombay, India. Amputees' physical and mental scores were significantly lower than those of the general population (Kumar and Vinita, 2021). One Turkish study that compared patients with post-polio syndrome to a control group without post-polio syndrome found that post-polio patients had lower QOL in terms of their physical mobility, pain, and energy.

QOL in prosthetic and orthotic users in relation to gender

According to our research, there are no appreciable disparities between disabled men and women (Magnusson et al., 2019). This is consistent with a systematic evaluation of the literature, which discovered that just three of the 26 research on people with amputations that were included indicated significantly poorer QOL for women than for males.

Yet, in the areas of physical health and environmental quality of life, men with disabilities dramatically underperformed individuals without disabilities. This is consistent with research on male leprosy patients in India. Contrary to the findings of a different Indian study, which found that female leprosy patients' scores indicated lower QOL than the female reference groups in the psychological domain, women with disabilities in our study had lower QOL than women without disabilities in the physical health domain. Variations in samples or types of disability could be one reason for this discrepancy (Sinha and Van Den Heuvel, 2011).

QOL for prosthetic and orthotic users in relation to income, education, and area of residence

According to our findings, people who had no income or inconsistent income and had not attended school were more likely to have worse QOL across all four domains: physical health, psychological well-being, social interactions, and environment (Magnusson et al., 2019). The findings showed that characteristics associated with good HRQOL included greater education and employment following an amputation. A study conducted in Bangladesh on people who had mobility disabilities discovered a favourable correlation between using wheelchairs and lower levels of poverty. Our findings also show that the subgroup residing in slums was more likely to have lower QOL in the areas of environment, psychological health, and physical health.

According to an Indian study that used the SF-36 to identify QOL-influencing characteristics in lower-limb amputees, co-morbidities, residual stump pain, phantom limb pain, and employment status all strongly predicted both physical and mental HRQOL (Magnusson et al., 2019). The majority of studies lacking background data on factors including education, occupation, economic situation, and marital status, according to the systematic evaluation of QOL studies of amputees.

Process of prosthetics production

The production process of prosthetics involves a combination of technology, design, and skilled labor. The process can vary depending on the type of prosthetic device, the material used, and the individual needs of the patient. However, here is a general overview of the production process of prosthetics (Barrios-Muriel et al., 2020)

Assessment and evaluation: Before producing a prosthetic device, the patient's condition and needs must be evaluated. This includes assessing the patient's physical condition, taking measurements, and considering the patient's lifestyle and preferences. This information is used to design a prosthetic device that meets the patient's needs and fits properly.

Design: Once the patient's needs are understood, a prosthetist will create a custom design for the prosthetic device. The design process may involve using computer-aided design (CAD) software to create a virtual model of the device.

Casting or scanning: Next, the patient's residual limb is casted or scanned to create a 3D model of the limb. This model is used to create a socket, which is the part of the prosthetic device that attaches to the residual limb.

Fabrication: Once the socket is created, the rest of the prosthetic device is fabricated. This may involve using a variety of materials, including plastics, metals, and composites. The materials are shaped and assembled to create the components of the prosthetic device.

Fitting and adjustments: Once the prosthetic device is fabricated, it is fitted to the patient's residual limb. The prosthetist will adjust ensure that the device fits properly and is comfortable for the patient.

Training and follow-up: After the prosthetic device is fitted, the patient will receive training on how to use and care for the device. Follow-up appointments are also scheduled to ensure that the prosthetic device is functioning properly and to make any necessary adjustments.

Overall, the production process of prosthetics requires a skilled team of professionals, including prosthetists, designers, and technicians. The process is highly personalized, with each device being custom-made to meet the unique needs of the patients (Angajala et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2020).

3DPro—Development of Low-Cost Prosthetics Using 3D Printing Technologies

The concept of utilizing 3D printing for medical applications is not a novel idea. It has been applied in the production of implants such as teeth, bones, and jaws. However, the printing of personalized prosthetics for hands and legs is still being developed (Zagel et al., 2017). While the idea of producing low-cost prosthetics is often discussed as a vision for the future, current research and applications are primarily focused on developing prosthetics for use in the modern world. Therefore, there is a strong emphasis on using high-quality medical materials that meet the standard requirements (Zagel and Süßmuth, 2013).

We are using affordable depth cameras like the Microsoft Kinect game controller as the technical foundation for our project. The algorithms developed for a previously engineered Kinect-based body scanner will serve as the groundwork for our 3D stump-reconstruction project (Vaezi et al., 2013). This allows for accurate digital representations of human bodies to be generated. Our system has potential uses in the medical field and for providing dress size recommendations in online shops. By automating the production of construction files, this approach makes the system easy to use for practitioners without specialized technical knowledge (Bomsdorf et al., 2015). We plan to develop the prototype further so that it can detect single body parts with high accuracy. The 3D model of the body part, such

as a leg stump, will be automatically measured and converted into a negative model, resulting in a 3D image of a prosthesis stem.

We plan to make the system portable by transferring it onto a tablet PC or smartphone to improve mobile usability. Additionally, we aim to create a cosmetic approximation of the prosthesis by using a full-body scan to "mirror" a healthy leg, which is especially important in developing countries. While attempts are being made to reconstruct complete prosthetic limbs, our focus is primarily on creating the shaft, which must be customized to fit the texture and shape of the stump. In the **second part** of the process, we will use plastic waste from items like cups and bottles, which will be processed into printable filaments using an extruder. The individual prosthesis will be printed based on the previously calculated virtual shaft model. Post-processing techniques such as removing burrs and attaching a silicone layer will be used to improve wearability and comfort. We conducted printing and material tests in a laboratory setting as part of the sub-processes, and stress test values are transferred into simulations of 3D models to validate the basic feasibility of the process.

Finite-element analysis of prostheses and orthoses design and assessment

In AM fabrication, a design is expected to be well fitted to the patient without further modification of the design. An assessment system that can predict and design an appropriate fit in advance of fabrication is necessary. Computational analysis provides a feasible tool for this purpose. Finite-element analysis was introduced to prosthetic socket and orthosis design in the late 1980s ([Zhang et al., 1998](#)). The system can analyze stress distribution in both human body tissues and prosthetic or orthotic components, identify how loads are transferred, and determine biomechanical behaviors at the contact interface between the body and the prosthesis or orthosis. To achieve the desired functional performance, topology optimization of the design based on finite-element predictions is an effective approach (Liu et al., 2018). Finite-element analysis was used to identify the effects [of material properties](#), thickness, and size on the stiffness of the device. The size-dependent variables were determined through [regression functions](#) based on finite-element analysis.

After calculating the material parameters, computations of different geometries and structures were conducted, taking into account direction-dependent material data (Banga et al., 2018). This enables the assessment of component firmness before actually printing new parts, reducing the need for time- and material-consuming stress tests. The infill inside the 3D model, which refers to its interior structure, can be customized in terms of both quantity and structure using 3D printing software. The appropriate infill structure is crucial for achieving the optimal balance between weight and stability for prosthetic construction. Various infill structures such as grids, diagonal, or honeycomb structures are available in printing software applications, and stress tests have been carried out (fixed clamping, 10N strain) to compare their performance. The honeycomb structure (26.5mm) was found to have significantly stronger deflection than the grid structure (14mm), likely due to its evenly distributed stiffness in all load directions (Banga et al., 2018).

A study proposed testing the breaking resistance of an AM-fabricated ankle-foot orthosis under frequency and temperature loads using finite-element analysis ([Chen et al., 2016](#)). In a study on the AM fabrication of passive-dynamic ankle-foot orthoses, finite-element models of the orthoses were used to determine the cross-sectional strut dimensions (Faustini et al., 2008). To determine the optimized approach among different manufacturing methods, a comparison was conducted of the processes, materials, and [material thicknesses](#) while balancing cost, production time, and patient performance for various ankle-foot orthoses (Totah et al., 2017).

ConclusionIn conclusion, 3D printing and the use of recyclable plastics have brought about significant advancements in the production of prosthetics. This technology has made it possible to create customized, affordable, and high-quality prosthetics, particularly in developing countries where access to traditional prosthetics can be limited. The use of recycled plastics in the process has also added to the sustainability of the process, reducing waste and making it more environmentally friendly. The growing interest in 3D printing technology for prosthetics production in countries like India is a promising development that has the potential to greatly improve the lives of people with disabilities. With continued innovation and investment, this technology can be further improved to provide even better solutions for those in need of prosthetics.

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